

Development of a Learning Model for Basic Underhand Passing Technique in Volleyball Through Volleyball Tennis Game for Eighth Grade Students of SMP Dharma Wanita Kota Surabaya

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to develop the Basic Movement Technique Learning of Underhand Passing in Volleyball Through Volleyball Tennis Games for Grade VIII Students of SMP DHARMA WANITA CITY OF SURABAYA so that it can make students happier, more active, creative, and motivated to play volleyball. The expected product is a pocket book of learning models for underhand passing and Volleyball Tennis games. The method used in this study is development research by modifying research steps that are appropriate to conditions in the field. Data collection was carried out using questionnaires for experts and students. With the qualification of 1 physical education teacher, and for trials used small groups of 14 students and large groups of 32 students. The results of the validation of media experts showed that the average value was 3.4 and material experts showed that the average value was 3.30. The conclusion of this study based on data collected from volleyball experts, learning experts and students when conducting trials paying attention to the results of data analysis that has been done, then all learning models are feasible and can be used.

KEYWORDS: Development, Volleyball, Learning Model, Volleyball Tennis.

A. INTRODUCTION

Volleyball games at school are an integral part of Physical Education, Sports, and Health learning. According to Endang Pratiwi (2020: 2), volleyball is a branch of sports that is widely known by all levels of society and has gained international recognition. This is because volleyball has been played in many competitions. The fundamental reason for including volleyball as a subject in Physical Education, Sports, and Health classes is the demand of the educational curriculum. According to Prasetyo et al. (2020), Physical Education is a field of study that often involves direct learning and the utilization of sports facilities. This is intended to help students acquire knowledge, understanding, and skills related to volleyball itself. In addition, through volleyball games, students are expected to develop a sense of sportsmanship and, most importantly, improve their physical health.

Volleyball game material in schools, especially at the junior high school (SMP) level, is implemented based on learning principles, with the main goal being to improve basic skills as well as to instill values such as discipline, cooperation, sportsmanship, respect for opponents, and tolerance. According to Musitoh & Rijal (2018), Physical Education is essentially an educational process that involves physical activity and concerns changes in individual characteristics, including physical, social, emotional, and intellectual development.

According to Juliansyah (2021), the basic techniques of volleyball that need to be mastered include passing, serving, smashing, and blocking. One of the basic volleyball movements taught at the junior high school level is passing, which consists of overhead passing and underhand passing. Passing is defined as receiving an attack from the opponent or acting as a set-up for a teammate. Passing is a fundamental technique that must be mastered by volleyball players; therefore, this basic passing technique becomes an inseparable part of volleyball learning at school, particularly at the junior high school level.

B. METHOD

The development research model used by the author is Research and Development (R&D), as stated by Sugiyono (2018). This type of research aims to produce a specific product and test the effectiveness of that product. R&D research is defined as "an educational research and development process that involves the creation and validation of educational products." There are various development research models that can serve as references in R&D studies. According to Amali (2019), several models can be applied in research and development. Furthermore, Sugiyono (2021) explains that the R&D method is a scientific approach used to

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investigate, design, produce, and validate a developed product. The resulting product can either be a completely new item or a modification of an existing one.

Other researchers have also defined development research in education as a study aimed at producing instructional products, which involves stages such as needs analysis, product development, product evaluation, review, and diffusion (Mushofi, 2017). Based on the above descriptions, the author concludes that a development research model is an effort to create a product and examine its effectiveness through various stages of product evaluation, with the aim of enhancing the teaching and learning process.

Table 1. Scoring Criteria for Volleyball Development Assessment

Criteria	Score
Very Good	4
Good	3
Fairly Good	2
Very Poor	1

The results of the assessment are then averaged and converted using the score conversion criteria. The conversion is presented in **Table 2**:

Table 2. Score Criteria for Volleyball Development Assessment

Skor Kualitas	Kriteria Kevalidan	Keterangan
$3,26 \leq x \leq 4,00$	Valid	No. revision required
$2,51 \leq x \leq 3,25$	Fairly Valid	Partial revision
$1,76 \leq x \leq 2,50$	Less Valid	Requires revision and content review
$1,00 \leq x \leq 1,75$	Not Valid	Total revision needed

C. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research can be conducted by identifying both opportunities and problems. In this study, the opportunity lies in the fact that SMP Dharma Wanita Kota Surabaya already has volleyball facilities, including nets and school yard infrastructure, which can be optimally utilized by teachers and students. Secondly, these facilities can be used to improve underhand passing skills in volleyball through the development of a Volleyball Tennis game model. The problem observed among the subjects is that the current learning process is still contextual-based, leading to low student enthusiasm. Product development is expected to address this issue by creating a customized Volleyball Tennis game model. Instead of solely relying on potential and problems, the researcher also refers to up-to-date documentary evidence from activity reports by individuals or relevant authorities.

The data collection method used by the researcher involved field data collection. The researcher conducted observations at SMP Dharma Wanita Kota Surabaya to identify problems in the volleyball learning process. By observing and reviewing actual teaching activities particularly when students were practicing underhand passing the researcher gathered relevant insights. Based on these observations, the researcher will develop a modified Volleyball Tennis game model for teaching underhand passing, using questionnaires and expert validation as instruments.

The aspects and indicators to be assessed by media experts were designed to evaluate the Volleyball Tennis pocketbook in terms of media usability. The media expert evaluation of the pocketbook resulted in an average score of 3.30 out of a maximum of 4.0, indicating that the development falls into the "Good" category. The feasibility assessment of the Volleyball Tennis pocketbook obtained an average score of 3.4 out of 4.0, again placing it in the "Good" category. Based on the product trial results, which showed the feasibility of the modified Volleyball Tennis game model, the research proceeded to the implementation trial stage. After a successful product trial, the modified Volleyball Tennis game model was applied in a large group consisting of 32 eighth-grade students from SMP Dharma Wanita Kota Surabaya, selected systematically. The student learning motivation questionnaire related to the development of the Volleyball Tennis pocketbook yielded an average score of 3.5 out of 4.0, indicating that the product falls into the "Good" category in terms of its impact on student learning motivation.

The Student t-test results showed that $t\text{-table} (-2.030) < t\text{-count} (-2.488)$, thus the hypothesis decision is to accept H1 and reject H0, which means at a 95% confidence level, there is a significant difference between the sample mean and the standard mean of student motivation.

The media expert validation yielded an average score of 3.4, and the subject matter expert validation resulted in an average of 3.30. Based on expert evaluations, the Volleyball Tennis pocketbook is considered feasible for trials, with revisions as per expert

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suggestions. The student learning motivation questionnaire again produced an average score of 3.49, reaffirming the product's positive impact on motivation.

The final development result of the Volleyball Tennis pocketbook, as evaluated by PJOK subject teachers, yielded an average score of 3.4. According to the teacher's evaluation, the pocketbook is feasible for trial implementation with revisions aligned to expert recommendations.

D. CONCLUSIONS

The Volleyball Tennis game is declared feasible for trial implementation with revisions based on expert suggestions. The student learning motivation questionnaire yielded an average score of 3.49, indicating that the development of the Volleyball Tennis pocketbook falls into the "Good" category in terms of enhancing students' learning motivation.

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